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An Upper Bound for the Generalized Atom-Bond Connectivity Index of a Graph

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Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. The generalized atom-bond connectivity index of a graph G is defined as $\sum_{uv \in E} \left(\frac{d(u)+d(v)-2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha$, where α is a nonzero real number and $d(u)$ and $d(v)$ denote the degrees of vertices u and v in G , respectively. In this note, we present an upper bound for the generalized atom-bond connectivity index of a graph G with $\alpha > 0$.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notations and terminologies not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges, the degree of a vertex v

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is denoted by $d_G(v)$. We use δ and Δ to denote the minimum degree and maximum degree of G , respectively. The complement of a graph G is denoted by G^c . We use $G[S]$ to denote a subgraph of G induced by a subset S of V . A set of vertices in a graph G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . For disjoint vertex subsets X and Y of $V(G)$, we use $E(X, Y)$ to denote the set of all the edges in $E(G)$ such that one end vertex of each edge is in X and another end vertex of the edge is in Y . Namely, $E(X, Y) := \{f : f = xy \in E, x \in X, y \in Y\}$.

A variety of topological indexes for graphs such as Wiener index [8], Randić index [6], and the first Zagreb index [5] have been introduced. In 1998, Estrada, Torres, Rodríguez, and Gutman [4] introduced the atom–bond connectivity index (*ABC*-index) of a graph G , denoted $ABC(G)$, which is defined as

$$ABC(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} \left(\frac{d(u) + d(v) - 2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Furtula, Graovac, and Vukičević [3] extended the concept of the atom-bond connectivity index to the concept of the generalized atom-bond connectivity index, denoted $ABC_\alpha(G)$, which is defined as

$$ABC_\alpha(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} \left(\frac{d(u) + d(v) - 2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha.$$

where α is nonzero real number. Obviously, $ABC_\alpha(G)$ becomes $ABC(G)$ when $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$. Some results on the generalized atom-bond connectivity index of a graph can be found in [2] [7].

In this note, we present an upper bound for the generalized atom–bond connectivity index of a graph with $\alpha > 0$. The result is as follows.

Theorem 1. Let G be a graph with n vertices and $\delta \geq 1$. Then

$$ABC_\alpha(G) \leq \beta(n - \beta) \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{(n - \beta)\Delta} \right) \right)^\alpha$$

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$$+ \frac{(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{2} \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \right) \right)^\alpha$$

with equality if and only if G is K_n .

2 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. Suppose G is a graph with n vertices and $\delta \geq 1$. Let I be an independent set such that $|I| = \beta$. Then $1 \leq \beta \leq n - 1$ and $1 \leq n - \beta \leq n - 1$. Clearly, $d(x) \leq n - \beta$ for each $x \in I$ and $d(y) \leq \Delta$ for each $y \in V - I$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} S_1 &= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in I, v \in V - I} \left(\frac{d(u) + d(v) - 2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in I, v \in V - I} \left(\frac{1}{d(u)} + \frac{1}{d(v)} - \frac{2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha \\ &\leq \sum_{uv \in E, u \in I, v \in V - I} \left(\frac{1}{\delta} + \frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{2}{(n - \beta)\Delta} \right)^\alpha \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in I, v \in V - I} \left(\frac{1}{\delta} + \frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{2}{(n - \beta)\Delta} \right)^\alpha \\ &= \beta(n - \beta) \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{(n - \beta)\Delta} \right) \right)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

We further have

$$\begin{aligned} S_2 &:= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in V - I, v \in V - I, u \neq v} \left(\frac{d(u) + d(v) - 2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E, u \in V - I, v \in V - I, u \neq v} \left(\frac{1}{d(u)} + \frac{1}{d(v)} - \frac{2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in V - I, v \in V - I, u \neq v} \left(\frac{1}{d(u)} + \frac{1}{d(v)} - \frac{2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in V - I, v \in V - I, u \neq v} \left(\frac{1}{\delta} + \frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{2}{\Delta\Delta} \right)^\alpha \end{aligned}$$

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$$= \frac{(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{2} \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \right) \right)^\alpha.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} ABC_\alpha(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E} \left(\frac{d(u) + d(v) - 2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha = S_1 + S_2 \\ &\leq \beta(n - \beta) \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{(n - \beta)\Delta} \right) \right)^\alpha \\ &\quad + \frac{(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{2} \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \right) \right)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

If

$$\begin{aligned} ABC_\alpha(G) &= \beta(n - \beta) \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{(n - \beta)\Delta} \right) \right)^\alpha \\ &\quad + \frac{(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{2} \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \right) \right)^\alpha \end{aligned}$$

In reviewing the proofs above, we have that $d(x) = \delta = n - \beta$ for each $x \in I$ and thereby $xy \in E$ for each $x \in I$ and each $y \in V - I$, $d(y) = \delta = \Delta$ for each $y \in V - I$, and $G[V - I]$ is a complete graph. Thus for each $y \in V - I$ we have $d(y) = \delta = \Delta = (n - 1)$. Therefore G is K_n .

If G is K_n , a simple computation yields

$$\begin{aligned} ABC_\alpha(G) &= \beta(n - \beta) \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{(n - \beta)\Delta} \right) \right)^\alpha \\ &\quad + \frac{(n - \beta)(n - \beta - 1)}{2} \left(2 \left(\frac{1}{\delta} - \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \right) \right)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

Hence we complete the proof of Theorem 1.

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